

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Herbal Drug Used For The Treatment Of Hypertension

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ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05 July 2024

Accepted: 14 July 2024

Published: 15 July 2024

Keywords:

Hypertension, Obesity, herbal medicines, therapeutic agents

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.12818423

ABSTRACT

The review focus on Indian herbal medicine and shops used to treat hypertension .The purpose of this review to give information on current knowledge aquired in preclinical and clinical studies. Hypertension is the medical term for high blood pressure. It is dangerous because it makes the heart work to hard cand contributes to atherosclerosis, besides increasing the risk of heart disease and stroke. Hypertension can also leads to other conditions Such as congestive heart failure, kidney disease and blindness. Conventional antihypertensives are usually associated with many side effects.

INTRODUCTION

Hypertension of high Blood pressure is a chronic medical condition in which the BP in the arteries is elevated. It is classified as either primary of secondary.About 90 to 95% of cases are termed primary hypertension which refers to high BP for which no medical cause can be found.The remaining 5 to 10% of cases, called Secondary hypertension, are caused by other conditions that affect the kidney, arteries, heart or endocrine system. Exercise hypertension is an excessively high elevation in BP during exercise. The range considered Normal for Systolic values during exercise is between 200 and 280 mm Hg. Exercise hypertension may indicate that an individual is at risk for developing hypertension at rest.

Causes

- 1) Hypokalemia
- 2) Obesity
- 3) Salt sensitivity
- 4) Alcohol intake
- 5) Risk also increases with aging

Anti-Hypertensive drug

Anti-Hypertensive drug, which are used to treatment of high blood pressure. Many antihypertensive agent used in the treatment of hypertension have some side effects. Therefore, scientific Studies recommend diverse lifestyle alterations and the use of suitable medicinal plants in its treatment.

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Ayurvedic herbs like Alfalfa, chicory, Ginger, Garlic and Ginseng are believed to help lower high blood pressure due to their natural properties such as reducing Stress, promoting relaxation and improving blood circulation.

Herbal drug used to hypertension

A. Alfalfa

Source

It is the entire plant of medicago Sativa belonging to the Family: Fabaceae.

Chemical Constituents

1. Leaves, sprouts and seed contain vitamin-K, vitamin-C., Copper, manganese, folate, thiamin riboflavin, magnesium and iron.
2. One cup of sprouts contains one gram of protein and one of carbohydrates.
3. It has also has a high content of bioactive compounds like saponin coumarin, Flavonoids, phytosterols, phytoestrogens and alkaloids.

Uses

It is used as-

- 1) Hypocholesteremic
- 2) Anti-hypertension
- 3) Diuretic
- 4) Galactagogue
- 5) Anti-arthritis
- 6) To treat Kidney stones
- 7) Anti diabetic

8) To relieve menopausal symptoms.

9) Antioxidant.

B. Chicory

Source

It is obtained from the plant Cichorium intybus, belonging to the family: Asteraceae.

Chemical Constituents

Chicory contains a variety of nutrients which include carbohydrates, proteins, vitamins, minerals, Soluble fiber, phenolics, insulin, coumarins, tannins, monomeric flavonoids, sesquiterpene lactones and beta carotene.

Uses

The roots are used as-

- 1) A Coffee Substitute and additive.
- 2) They are mixed in Indian filter coffee.
- 3) Used in high blood pressure, heart failure, Loss of appetite, stomach upset, constipation, Cancer liver and gall bladder, disorders, inflammation and hepatic toxicity.

C. Ginger:

Source

It is the dried rhizomes of *Zingiber officinale* belonging to the family : Zingiberaceae.

Chemical Constituents

- 1) It contains volatile oils, minerals, resins.

- 2) Gringer Oil contains Zingiberine, bisabolone, farnesene, Sesquiphellandrene and curcumene.

- 3) Resins contain phenolic ketones such as gingerols, Shogaols, zingerone and other compounds.

Uses

ginger is used as:

- 1) Stomachic
- 2) Aromatic
- 3) Carminative
- 4) stimulant
- 5) Flavouring agent
- 6) In ginger beverages
- 7) Adsorbent of toxins From GIT
- 8) To control parasitic infections.

D. Garlic:

Source

It consists of dried bulbs of *Allium Sativum*, belonging to the family: Liliaceae.

Chemical Constitutents

1. Garlic contains, carbohydrates, proteins, fats, mucilage volatile oils and minerals.
2. The volatile oil contain allin, allicin, allyl propyl disulfide., diallyl disulfide, minerals contains phosphorous, iron and copper.

Uses

It is used as-

- 1) Carminative
- 2) Aphrodisiac
- 3) Expectorant
- 4) Stimulant
- 5) Disinfectant
- 6) Anthelmintic
- 7)Antibacterial
- 8)Antihypertensive
- 9) Hypocholestromic.

E. Ginseng

Source

It consist of soots of the plant panax ginseng and other Species of Panax, belonging to the family: Araliaceae.

Chemical Constituent

Ginseng contains saponins, glycosider, volatile oils, sterols polysaccharides,

minerals, vitamin - B1, B2, B12 Pantothenic acid and biotin.

Uses

It is used as-

- 1) Adaptogenic
- 2) It relieves Stress and fatigue
- 3) Used in hypertension; diabetes, psychogenic important and child psychiatric disorders.

CONCLUSION

The concomitant use of herbal medicines and pharmacotherapy is spreading widely. Hence, it becomes mandatory to explore the possible interactions of these drugs with present day therapeutic agents. Such an approach would help to reduce the risk of any potential interaction as well as help in providing adequate therapeutic benefits to the end uses. Here, we have reviewed the literature to determine the possible interactions between herbal medicine and antihypertensive drugs. These interactions show that herbal medicine may alter the bioavailability and

pharmacokinetic parameter of drugs. Pharmacodynamic interactions may produce synergistic or antagonistic effect. Thus, it is necessary to consider herbal medicines as regular medicines and explore the possibility of interaction with concomitantly administered drugs. The interaction with herb may be beneficial, harmful or may reduced the effect of prescribed drug. Hence, combine use of herbal with antihypertensive medications should only be done after consultation with a physician. Preliminary research data on combination of herbals and drugs is to be provided to educate pharmacists and physicians for safe and efficacious use of drug and encourage further clinical research.

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HOW TO CITE: Shital Sagale, Satish Sagale, Herbal Drug Used For The Treatment Of Hypertension, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 7, 1820-1824. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12818423>

